

Reaction of 2-propanol over alumina in the presence of methyl acetate. Evidence for the nature of adsorption

J. R. Jain

Chemistry Department, Kirori Mal College, Delhi University Campus, Delhi-110 007, India

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Dehydration of 2-propanol over alumina at 280° has been studied in the presence of methyl acetate as a co-reactant. Even as low as 2 mol% of methyl acetate strongly inhibits the dehydration reaction (alkene and ether formation). Co-adsorption of methyl acetate leads to the formations of 2-propyl acetate (ester exchange) and methyl 2-propyl ether (ether formation) as competing reactions at low concentrations of methyl acetate and the only reactions at more than 50 mol% of methyl acetate.

The cooperative role of acidic and basic sites on the surface is generally recognised in the catalytic activity of alumina, various oxides and metal catalysts surfaces¹⁻³. One of the earliest studies on this topic relates to the dehydration of alcohols over alumina¹ and later studies⁴⁻⁶ confirm this concept. The addition of a co-reactant which may have an inhibiting or enhancing effect⁵ on the reaction of a particular substance has been widely reported in order to understand the nature of surface sites^{2,6}. The use of bases to block acidic sites and inhibit acid-catalysed reactions in an obvious and well known example of such an approach. In the present study, the effect of an ester, methyl acetate, on the reaction of 2-propanol over alumina is reported.

Results and Discussion

The results of the reaction of 2-propanol + methyl acetate are presented in Table 1. Temperature and contact time were kept low so that conversions were low in order to minimise side-reactions and deactivation of the catalyst. In addition to the product listed, acetic acid and water were formed which were not analysed.

2-Propanol reacted over alumina at 280° to give only dehydration products, namely, propene and 2-propyl ether (Table 1). Addition of just 2 mol% of methyl acetate (sl. no. 2) lowered propene formation by about 50% and 2-propyl ether by 26% and formation of methyl 2-propyl ether, 2-propyl acetate and methanol had already started. At this stage, the conversion of 2-propanol also decreased by about 41%, demonstrating the strong inhibiting effect of methyl acetate on the dehydration of 2-propanol. In this sense methyl acetate has a similar effect as bases like pyridine in poisoning the catalytic sites for dehydration¹. At higher concentration of methyl acetate there was steep reduction in the alkene and ether formation. At 20 mol%

(sl. no. 5) ether was absent and above 50 mol% (sl. no. 8) propene was also absent. Parallel with the inhibition of

(A) Ether formation :

(B) Alkene formation :

(C) Ester exchange

(D) Mixed ether formation :

A- and -B- are acidic and basic sites on alumina surface.

Similar scheme can be obtained by replacing 2-propanol by phenol to form the corresponding products, such as anisole, phenyl acetate etc.

Scheme 1

these products arising from the reaction of 2-propanol with methyl acetate, namely, methyl 2-propyl ether, 2-propyl

Table 1. Reactions of 2-propanol in the presence of methyl acetate

Sl. no.	Reactants (mol)		%Conversion*	Products (mol)				
	2-Propanol	Methyl acetate		Propene	2-Propyl ether	Methyl 2-propyl ether	2-Propyl acetate	Methanol
1.	0.50	—	30.15	0.127	0.013	—	—	—
2.	0.49	0.01	17.97	0.063	0.0093	0.0018	0.0040	0.0059
3.	0.475	0.025	11.14	0.026	0.0073	0.0030	0.0094	0.0097
4.	0.45	0.05	9.94	0.021	0.0029	0.0050	0.0129	0.013
5.	0.40	0.10	8.43	0.013	—	0.0064	0.0147	0.017
6.	0.35	0.15	7.86	0.005	—	0.0072	0.0149	0.016
7.	0.30	0.20	6.75	0.005	—	0.0065	0.0133	0.015
8.	0.25	0.25	5.32	0.003	—	0.0055	0.0127	0.016
9.	0.20	0.30	4.69	—	—	0.0050	0.0103	0.016
10.	0.15	0.35	3.23	—	—	0.0038	0.0100	0.014

* Based on 2-propanol.

acetate and methanol were formed. These products arose from the following reactions, namely, an ester exchange (reaction 1) and mixed ether formation (reaction 2).

While acid and base catalysed ester exchange called alcoholysis of ester is well known⁷, simultaneous mixed ether formation is unusual and not normally observed in homogeneous acid and base catalysed reactions between alcohol and ester specially on solid catalysts.

Formation of both ether and alkene from alcohol has been shown to involve the cooperative effect of acidic and basic sites as represented in Schemes 1A and 1B. The poisoning effect of methyl acetate showed that it competed with 2-propanol for the acidic sites, represented as -A- in Schemes 1C and 1D. Formation of surface 2-propoxy group by hydrogen abstractions by basic sites (-B-) was not inhibited by methyl acetate. Adsorption of methyl acetate on acidic site as represented in Scheme 1C (structure 1) made available positively charged methyl and acetyl groups as electrophiles. Thus the observed products arose by the nucleophilic attack by the surface 2-propoxy species at the two electrophilic sites (methyl carbon and acetyl carbon) of the adsorbed methyl acetate (Schemes 1C and 1D) simultaneously.

Of the two competing reactions, ester exchange was the preferred reaction as far as 2-propanol was concerned. Further insight into the reaction was obtained by the study of phenol + methyl acetate (Table 2). Phenol alone did not react

Table 2. Reactions of phenol and methyl acetate over alumina

Sl. no.	Reactants (mol)		Products (mol)		
	Phenol	Methyl acetate	Anisole	Phenyl acetate	Methanol
1.	0.3	0.2	0.0043	0.0012	0.0120
2.	0.2	0.3	0.0093	0.0020	0.0140
3.	0.5	0.0	Even the traces of diphenyl ether was not formed.		

over alumina as reported earlier¹, but in the presence of methyl acetate, both phenyl acetate and anisole were formed. However, in this case, the selectivity was in favour of anisole (i.e. mixed ether formation) rather an ester exchange, showing that the selectivity in the nucleophilic attack at the two sites on the adsorbed methyl acetate depended upon the nature of the nucleophile. Alkoxide (2-propoxide) selectively attacked the (acyl) carbon and phenoxide selectively attacked the alkyl (methyl) carbon III. An equimolar mixture of phenol and acetic acid under the present experimental condition did not yield any phenyl acetate. The starting mixture was recovered unchanged. This probably means that phenol being very poor in an acidic nature in comparison to acetic acid was not at all adsorbed in presence of acetic acid⁸ and also probably activation of adsorbed acetic acid to provide acetyl cation did not take place unlike that of methyl acetate though aliphatic esterifications have already been established^{8,9}.

Conclusion : Methyl acetate strongly inhibited the dehydration of 2-propanol over alumina. It could be concluded that this inhibition occurred because methyl acetate was adsorbed on the acidic sites more strongly than 2-propanol. The adsorbed methyl acetate could react with nucleophile both at the acetyl carbon and at the methyl carbon. The consequent reactions are ester-exchange and mixed ether formation, the latter not usually observed in homogeneous acid and base catalysed reaction of alcohol with ester⁷ specially on solid catalysts. When phenol was

the co-reactant with methyl acetate, mixed ether formation (anisole) was the preferred reaction compared to ester exchange (phenyl acetate), demonstrating the importance of the nature of the nucleophile in the selectivity for ester or ether.

Experimental

Different reactions with different percentage compositions of reactants, namely, 2-propanol + methyl acetate, phenol + methyl acetate, and phenol + acetic acid were made to flow from top to bottom of a glass reactor, first through a preheater zone of pyrex glass chips and then over a bed of 1/8" alumina pellets (6 g). Alumina had a Na⁺ content of 0.1% as Na₂O and surface area 165 m² g⁻¹. The temperature was maintained at 280°. Reactants in different molar ratios were taken, but the total number of moles of the two reactants was maintained at 0.5. The flow rate was so adjusted that this amount of reactant mixture was passed over the catalyst bed in 1h. The effluent stream of products along with unconverted reactants was analysed by gas chromatography. Gaseous product propene was separately collected and analysed/monitored.

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